

“Exposure Assessment in Nitrates”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Nitrates are formed from fertilizers, decaying plants, manure and other organic residues. Nitrates can be found in the air, soil, water and food (particularly in vegetables). The presence of nitrates in vegetables, as in water and generally in food, is a serious threat to human health because is converted in saliva and the gastrointestinal tract to the toxic nitrite and other N-nitroso compounds, that can lead to severe pathologies in humans. The acceptable daily intake (ADI) for nitrate established is of 3.7 mg/kg body weight (bw) per day.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary nitrate (NO₃⁻) intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the ADI and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary NO₃⁻ exposure.

Mean dietary Nitrates exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 647 and 1709 µg/kg b.w. per day for mean and high consumers, respectively. It was found that only 0.6 % of the whole population was exposed over the ADI value of 3700 µg/Kg b.w. per day. Much higher exposure was observed for infants and toddlers due to their lower body weight and may be from the consumption of food prepared by fresh vegetables at home.

Potatoes (23.6%), Lettuces, salads (21.6%), Aromatic herbs, such as parsley, mint, dill, (15.1%), Spinach leaves (10.3%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Nitrates intake. Drinking water has also important contribution to Nitrates intake.

2 Introduction

Nitrate is a naturally occurring form of nitrogen and is an integral part of the nitrogen cycle in the environment. Nitrate is formed from fertilizers, decaying plants, manure and other organic residues. It can be found in the air, soil, water and food (particularly in vegetables). The presence of nitrate in vegetables, as in water and generally in food, is a serious threat to human health. Nitrate itself is relatively non-toxic, but is converted in saliva and the gastrointestinal tract to the more toxic nitrite and other N-nitroso compounds, that can lead to severe pathologies in humans. The European Commission (EC) in order to protect public health has established maximum levels of nitrate in lettuce and spinach. The acceptable daily intake (ADI) for nitrate established is of 3.7 mg/kg body weight (bw) per day.

2.1 Background

Two previous exposure assessments of Nitrates have been performed using the excel based version of the ImproRisk either food consumption data obtained from the Child Health Database for adolescents (11-15 years) developed in 2003 in Cyprus or the consumption data obtained from the EUMenu project carried out in the years 2014-2018. In both cases, occurrence and consumption data were codified using the FoodEx1 classification system.

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the dietary nitrate (NO₃-) intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the acceptable daily intake (ADI) of 3.7 mg/kg body weight (b.w.) per day and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary NO₃- exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

Nitrates occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2008-2020. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Since, in all cases left-censored results were below 30%, occurrence results below the LOD were set to half the LOD for the Middle-bound scenario.

In this study, an additional scenario with correction factors for loss of nitrates during the processing/cooking applied to fresh vegetables was also applied to the occurrence data, based on the following assumptions:

- Brassica vegetables and leafy vegetables are always washed before consumption and a factor of 0.75 was applied to the concentration levels;
- potatoes and potatoes products, new potatoes, main-crop potatoes are always consumed boiled and a factor of 0.57 was applied to the concentration levels;

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264).

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Nitrates summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Nitrates
Substance Category	Contaminant
Reference value	3700 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference value	Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Nitrates

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0	0	0
Max	9913.1	9948.7	9984.3
Mean	642.2	646.9	651.7
SD	641.9	643	644.2
P25	261.6	264.6	271.9
Median	471	475.1	477.8
P75	819.5	825	830.7
P95	1705.8	1708.8	1711.9
pctOver	0.6%	0.6%	0.7%

* pctOver: Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure were calculated as 647 and 1709 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). It was found that only at 0.6 % of the whole population was exposed over the ADI value of 3700 µg/Kg b.w. per day, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	9,948.7	660.6	726.8	264.6	458.6	845.7	1,780.9	0.9%
MALE	0	7,981.2	632.7	541.9	269.8	516.4	799.5	1,608.4	0.4%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	6,241.7	639.6	668.9	207.4	516.4	774.9	2,428.8	0.2%
Larnaka	0	5,824.3	594.2	501.9	264.3	438.2	797.1	1,780.9	0%

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Lefkosa	0	5,333.8	562.4	514.6	256.3	407.4	708.9	1,343.7	0.6%
Lemesos	0	9,948.7	770.2	871.7	316.0	575.2	933.1	1,947.0	1.6%
Pafos	0	4,081.9	724.9	563.3	292.5	574.4	900.6	2,169.8	0.1%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	26.9	4,145.7	644.7	553.9	289.4	520.0	825.0	1,519.8	0.7%
Adults	22.7	6,748.0	601.8	599.4	256.3	453.2	774.7	1,608.4	0.4%
Elderly	23.5	4,961.3	667.4	628.1	275.8	492.5	925.8	1,793.5	0.8%
Infants	0.0	9,948.7	1,219.9	1,636.0	0.0	614.9	1,772.5	4,576.6	8.5%
Other children	26.9	4,354.4	773.2	610.3	384.3	617.1	998.5	2,057.5	0.7%
Toddlers	15.5	5,457.4	1,171.5	1,002.0	501.4	861.9	1,540.2	3,287.4	4%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that infants and toddlers had much higher exposure (almost two times) than the other population classes due to their lower body weight. Also 8.5% of infants and 4% of the toddlers were exceeding the ADI for Nitrates intake. Investigating the consumption data it was observed that infants and toddlers were more exposed to Nitrates because of the consumption of food prepared by fresh vegetables at home.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figures 4.6 illustrate the mean exposure to Nitrates by population class and geographical area. It was found that some differences between the geographical areas were obtained for infants and toddlers, in contrast with the other population classes. This may be due to different consumption habits of infants and toddlers in different geographical areas

Mean Nitrates exposure (MB scenario)

Across Area and Population class

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total Nitrates exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. Potatoes (23.6%), Lettuces, salads (21.6%), Aromatic herbs, such as parsley, mint, dill, (15.1%), Spinach leaves (10.3%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Nitrates intake. Drinking water has also important contribution to Nitrates intake because large amounts of water are consumed by all population classes. Although potatoes have low Nitrate concentration levels, because of their high consumption, present the highest contribution in the total Nitrates exposure. These results are consistent to the EFSA findings. Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 3

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Nitrates Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Nitrates Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 3 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Contribution
Vegetables and vegetable products	Bulb vegetables	Spring onions and similar-	1.15%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Fruiting vegetables	Solanacea	4.33%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Contribution
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Head brassica	3.95%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Lettuces and salad plants	21.63%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Leafy vegetables	Spinach-type leaves	10.26%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-)	Carrots and similar-	3.86%
Vegetables and vegetable products	Herbs and edible flowers	Aromatic herbs	15.06%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Tropical root and tuber vegetables	2.98%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	23.59%
Water and water-based beverages	Drinking water	Unbottled water	4.51%
Water and water-based beverages	Drinking water	Bottled water	6.29%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of nitrate has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to nitrates.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Uncertainties regarding the influence of food processing and/or cooking on the nitrate levels in the processed food – ImproRisk limitation	+
Uncertainty of the analytical measurements	+/-
Uncertainty about the representativeness of samples concerning, country of origin, size, seasonal differences, specific type of vegetable	+/-
Extrapolation uncertainties affecting the estimation of food consumption	+
Uncertainty in recording food types	+/-
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as the estimation of nitrate concentrations in food commodities and selection of consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the samples is taken into account as nitrate concentration levels are affected by season and type of vegetable.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration (5).

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) data may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean dietary Nitrates exposure of the Cypriot population was calculated as 647 and 1709 µg/kg b.w. per day for mean and high consumers, respectively. It was found that only at 0.6 % of the whole population was exposed over the ADI value of 3700 µg/Kg b.w. per day. Much higher exposure was observed for infants and toddlers due to their lower body weight and may be from the consumption of food prepared by fresh vegetables at home.

There was no significant difference in Nitrates intake between genders, but difference were obtained in different geographical areas in the case of infants and toddlers, may be due to different consumption habits.

Potatoes (23.6%), Lettuces, salads (21.6%), Aromatic herbs, such as parsley, mint, dill, (15.1%), Spinach leaves (10.3%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Nitrates intake. Drinking water has also important contribution to Nitrates intake.

7 References

1. European Food Safety Authority; Use of the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database in Exposure Assessment. EFSA Journal 2011;9(3):2097. [34 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2097.
2. EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM); Scientific Opinion on possible health risks for infants and young children from the presence of nitrates in leafy vegetables. EFSA Journal 2010;8(12):1935. [42 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1935.
3. EFSA. 2011b. Evaluation of the FoodEx, the food classification system applied to the development of the EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. EFSA Journal 2011; 9(3):1970. [27 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.1970.
4. EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2006. Guidance of the Scientific Committee on a request from EFSA related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. The EFSA Journal. 438, 1-54.

8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)

Key	Description
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices